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**Chitosan - zeolite scaffold as a potential biomaterial in the controlled release of
drugs for osteoporosis**

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Abstract

Chitosan scaffolds are a potential material in many biomedical applications. A particularly interesting application is their use in bone tissue engineering. Because of their biocompatibility and nontoxicity, they are an ideal material for this application. What is missing from chitosan scaffolds is controlled drug release. They can obtain this property by adding drug carriers. In this work, chitosan-calcium zeolite scaffolds were prepared and used in the controlled release of the drug for osteoporosis - risedronate. Their properties have been compared with those of the popular chitosan-hydroxyapatite scaffold. The zeolite was evenly distributed throughout the scaffold. More drug was retained on the scaffold with the addition of zeolite compared to that with the hydroxyapatite. The new scaffolds have proven to be able to retain the drug and slowly release it in small doses. The results obtained are promising and show great potential for this material in bone tissue engineering.

Introduction

Chitosan is a carbohydrate biopolymer, which is one of the most studied natural biopolymers by scientists around the world. Chitosan is a deacetylated polysaccharide from chitin, a natural biopolymer found primarily in shells and fungi [1]. The great interest in this material comes from its great biodegradability, biocompatibility, bioactivity, and nontoxicity. The possibilities of its use in many biomedical applications are analyzed: as a drug carrier, part of wound dressings, and part of implants [2]. Chitosan is known as a material that supports the healing process of soft and hard connective tissues [3]. Chitosan has been shown to have antimicrobial activity both independently and synergistically, and is recognized as an antimicrobial biopolymer [4]. Because of its properties and ease to form nanoparticles, microparticles, nanofibers, beads, membranes, gels, sponge-like structures, and scaffolds can be made from it. Its use as the main scaffold element seems to be particularly interesting.

Porous chitosan scaffolds are prepared by controlled freezing and lyophilization of chitosan gels [5]. Chitosan scaffolds have been widely researched for their use in bone tissue engineering. The aim of a scaffold is to provide the structure and environment to allow and promote the ingrowth of tissue, with the eventual goal of degradation of the scaffold as well as replacement of new healthy tissue [6]. This biopolymer is particularly attractive as a bone scaffold, as it promotes the formation of hydroxyapatite, as well as the attachment and proliferation of osteoblast cells [7]. Many types of scaffolds have been tested and many fillers have been used in their preparation, for example: carbon nanotube [8], titanium dioxide [9], silicon dioxide, zirconia nanoparticles [10], polypyrrole [11] and silk fibroin [12]. Undoubtedly, the most commonly used fillers in chitosan compounds for bone regeneration are calcium

phosphates, especially hydroxyapatite [13–15]. Such a wide application of this filler is due to the fact that hydroxyapatite is the main component of human bones.

Due to increasing requirements for biomaterials, scaffolds, in addition to their basic properties, should also be capable of releasing drugs. The group of drugs that are used in the most common bone disease, osteoporosis, are bisphosphonates [16,17]. The release of these types of drugs from chitosan scaffolds may aid in faster recovery of the patient after surgery. However, it is required that the drug be released in low doses due to its toxicity in high doses [18]. Because of the high affinity of these drugs for calcium ions, their carrier may be material with divalent ions [19]. The popular chitosan-hydroxyapatite composite seems to be an ideal material for this type of application. Obviously, the amount of drug retained by such a scaffold will be satisfactory; however, the situation is not as good for drug release, which is more important. Only a small amount of drug is released from the surface of such materials and, in addition, the drug can be retained on the surface again [20,21]. The possibility of resorption on the hydroxyapatite-chitosan scaffold is because that the drug is not able to "decide" which type of hydroxyapatite to attach to - in the bone or the scaffold.

Zeolite fillers can be an important alternative to hydroxyapatite [22]. Zeolites are important materials in biotechnology and medicine. So far, they have been used in the delivery of drugs such as doxorubicin, gentamycin, aspirin, 5-fluorouracil, diclofenac [23]. Currently, there are studies in the literature that determine the usefulness of this type of filler in chitosan scaffolds [24,25]. Chitosan-zeolite scaffolds are capable of biomineralizing hydroxyapatite [26]. Zeolites were used in the controlled release of bisphosphonates for the first time by our team [27]. In our previous work, it was shown that the drug is released in small doses under the influence of simulated body fluids. This type of material was also applied to the modification of the titanium alloy surface,

where a release was also at controlled low doses [28]. In both studies, it was shown that the drug is retained only in the calcium form of zeolite, and in the case of the sodium form, sorption did not take place. Due to the effectiveness of the earlier materials, the preparation of a chitosan-zeolite scaffold can open up very wide possibilities in the release of drugs for osteoporosis. The research scheme for this work is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Release of the drug for osteoporosis from the chitosan-zeolite scaffold prepared in this work.

In this work, a chitosan-zeolite scaffold was obtained and used as a risedronate carrier. This is the first case of using the chitosan-zeolite composite as a scaffold that releases the drug under the influence of body fluids directly at the site of the disease. As a result of the deposition of the drug on a biocompatible scaffold, risedronate will be gradually released in the area of greatest demand. The main purpose of using this type of scaffold will be to release the drug for osteoporosis (risedronate) in small doses, which will reduce the toxicity of the drug and the side effects of therapy. Additionally, local drug delivery increases the osseointegration of the implant [29]. The chitosan-zeolite

scaffold was characterized to confirm the effectiveness of drug sorption. The sorption capacity and release rate of risedronate were also examined for the tested materials. For comparison, the same method was used to prepare a scaffold containing hydroxyapatite in its composition to determine the advantage of chitosan-zeolite material over those previously used.

Materials

Chitosan (medium molecular weight, 75-85 % deacetylation), sodium zeolite 13X (X, ~2 μm average particle size), calcium chloride, sodium risedronate (-RSD), tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane (TRIS), (99.8 %), sodium chloride (99 %), sodium bicarbonate (99 %), sodium sulfate (99 %), potassium phosphate dibasic trihydrate (99 %), potassium chloride (99 %) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrochloric acid (36-38 %) was obtained from Avantor.

Ion exchange

During ion exchange, 1 g of zeolite X was placed in 20 ml of 0.5 M calcium chloride solution for 24 hours. After being stirred (50 rpm), the zeolite was filtered. This process was repeated three times. The zeolite was then washed with distilled water three times and dried in an oven for 24 hours at 100 °C. The material after ion exchange was named CaX.

Preparation of scaffolds

In the first step, a 2 % chitosan solution was prepared in 10 ml of 1 % aqueous solution of acetic acid solution. The solution was stirred and heated on a magnetic stirrer at 50 °C for 2 hours. After this time, hydroxyapatite or zeolite was added to the solution in a 1:1 ratio to chitosan. The contents of the flask were mixed until a homogeneous solution was obtained. The liquid mixture was then poured into cylindrical molds and

placed in the freezer (-20 °C). The final step was to place the samples in a freeze dryer (Christ ALPHA 1-2 LDplus) to remove water for 24 hours.

Swelling ratio / Degradation rate

Swelling ratio (SR) studies were performed as follows. The scaffolds were placed in 20 ml of distilled water. The samples were removed from the water after 24 h. The excess water was drained and, after that, the samples were weighed. All measurements were repeated three times. The swelling ratio was calculated using the following formula:

$$SR = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{M_1} * 100 \% \quad (1)$$

where M_1 is the initial mass of the scaffold and M_2 is the mass of the scaffold after 24 h.

To measure the degradation rate (DR), the scaffolds were placed in 20 ml of distilled water and gently shaken for 24 hours. After that time, the samples were dried at 50°C for 24 hours. Three repetitions were made for each material. The degradation rate was calculated using the following formula:

$$DR = \frac{M_1 - M_3}{M_1} * 100 \% \quad (2)$$

where M_1 is the initial mass of the scaffold and M_3 is the final dry weight of the scaffold.

Drugs sorption

Drug sorption was initiated by the introduction of scaffolds into vials. The scaffolds were 9 mm in diameter and 2.5 mm in height. The tubes were filled with 6 ml of risedronate solution with a concentration of 0.1 mg*ml⁻¹ (solution in Tris-HCl buffer,

pH = 7.4). The samples were shaken on a laboratory shaker (150 rpm) for one week at room temperature. Six repetitions were made.

The same procedure was used for the chitosan scaffold, but the drug was not retained.

Drug Release

The scaffolds after drug sorption were placed in 1 ml of simulated body fluid (SBF) [27]. The samples were shaken on a laboratory shaker (150 rpm) at 36.6 °C. The amount of drug released was measured after each day for up to 30 days using UV-VIS spectroscopy. Each time, the SBF was replaced with a new portion to supply new ions.

X-ray Diffractometry (XRD).

Zeolite samples were examined by X-ray diffraction using a D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker, UK) with a Johanson monochromator and a LynxEye detector. The study was performed to exclude changes in the zeolite structure during ion exchange.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS).

SEM images were recorded using VEGA SEM (Tescan, Czech Republic). The SEM toll was equipped with an EDS analyzer (Bruker, UK). EDS was used to conduct the elemental analysis of the samples.

Zeta potential

Zeta potentials of the materials were determined with the use of a Zetasizer Nano ZS apparatus (Malvern Instruments Ltd., UK). The measurements were carried out at pH values ranging from 4 to 12, and the pH was adjusted with the use of hydrochloric acid and potassium hydroxide. The tested material (1mg/ml) was sonicated in an ultrasonic bath in distilled water for 1 minute.

Nitrogen Adsorption/Desorption Measurements.

The BET surface area and pore parameters of the obtained zeolites were determined by the nitrogen adsorption isotherm technique using an ASAP 2420 analyzer (Micromeritics, USA). Before experiments, the samples were outgassed at 200 °C in a vacuum chamber.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FT-IR analysis of the scaffolds was performed using a Vertex70 spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Germany). All materials were studied using a single reflection diamond ATR crystal.

Optical microscope

For the scaffolds obtained, microscopic examinations were performed to examine their morphological properties. Measurements were carried out with the use of an optical microscope (Motic 2000, Germany), equipped with a camera that allows for taking pictures of the viewed objects.

UV-VIS spectroscopy

UV-VIS spectrophotometer UV-2600 (Shimadzu, Japan) was applied for the determination of drug concentration during the sorption and release process. Measurements were made in the range of 230-300 nm (λ max=262 nm).

Statistical Analysis

All measurements were made in triplicate. Error bars are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation of three experiments. To examine the statistically significant differences one-way variance analysis was carried out at the significance level of 0.05.

All calculations were performed with the use of Statistica 13.1 software (TIBCO Software).

Results

In the first stage of this work, the effectiveness of ion exchange on a commercial zeolite X, which was used as a drug carrier, was proven. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the zeolite before and after ion exchange are shown in Figure 2. The shapes of the diffraction patterns before and after ion exchange are typical for the type FAU zeolite (X) with high crystallinity. The highest intensity peaks are at $\sim 6.1^\circ$, 15.4° , 20.1° , 23.3° , 26.8° , and 31° which is in line with the literature [30,31]. The main X-ray diffraction signals correspond to the planes of (111), (331), (440), (533), (642), and (662), respectively [30,32]. Apart from the high intensity diffraction signals, several medium to low-intensity diffraction signals are also observed in the XRD patterns of the zeolites. The results were compared to patterns (dotted line) from the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) and overlapped with them. Due to the lack of differences in the 2θ values, it can be concluded that the ion exchange did not affect the crystal structure of the zeolite. A comparison of the XRD patterns of zeolite X and CaX shows some intensity variations of the peaks resulting from the exchange of sodium ions with calcium ions [33]. Importantly, there are no additional intense peaks that could indicate the formation of, for example, calcium oxide or hydroxide. The efficiency of ion exchange is important because the deposition of calcium ions in the zeolite structure as a result of ion exchange will result in the release of the drug only under the influence of body fluids.

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of zeolite X and CaX.

Based on the SEM results, it can be seen that ion exchange does not affect the agglomeration of zeolite particles (Figure 3). The shape of the zeolites is typical of the zeolite X [34]. The absence of agglomeration is important because large agglomerated particles would be more difficult to distribute in the chitosan matrix. The particle size in both cases is in line with the manufacturer's data and averages about 2 μm . On the surface of the zeolite grains after ion exchange, there are no significant changes in relation to the grains before exchange. This indicated that calcium was not deposited on its surface in the form of chloride, oxide, or carbonate.

Figure 3. SEM images of zeolite X and CaX.

The lack of influence of ion exchange on the increase in agglomeration was also confirmed based on the zeta potential results (Figure 4). Measurements were made in a pH range from 2 to 10. It was observed that the zeta potential profiles had a similar shape for both materials. The only difference between the profiles is that the CaX profile is shifted down a few mV. The most important pH range that should be analyzed for these materials is pH 7-8. As can be seen, the differences between the two materials are statistically significant, but the changes are slight. CaX zeolite has a lower

zeta potential and hence is less prone to agglomeration. The zeta potential results prove that ion exchange does not increase the agglomeration of the zeolite.

Figure 4. Zeta potential curves of X and CaX zeolites.

The ion exchange efficiency was determined using the EDS technique (Figure 5). As can be seen after ion exchange, only a small amount of sodium is present in the zeolite structure, which proves the efficiency of the exchange. The amount of ions (Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) after ion exchange is similar to the amount of ions (Na^+) before the exchange. The reason is that calcium ions are almost twice as heavy, but there are two times less of them. In addition, the map of the distribution of calcium ions shows that they are present everywhere. There are no visible places with a high concentration of calcium ions, which also indirectly indicates that calcium ions are present in the structure of zeolites only because of ion exchange.

Figure 5. SEM images of zeolites. Elemental mapping of the same regions indicates the spatial distribution of sodium and calcium (by weight).

The lack of significant changes in the surface area and pore volume also indicates the effectiveness of ion exchange, and not, for example, the precipitation of calcium in other forms. The change can be seen in the average pore size, but this is only due to the fact that two sodium atoms are replaced with one calcium atom, resulting in larger pores [35].

Table 1. Characteristics of materials based on nitrogen adsorption/desorption Measurements.

	BET surface area [m ² *g ⁻¹]	total pore volume [cm ³ * g ⁻¹]	average pore width [nm]
X	645.32	0.32	2.01
CaX	606.95	0.32	2.14

The next stage of the research was the use of the obtained zeolite as a filler in chitosan scaffolds. The use of a scaffold containing calcium zeolite X and chitosan has great potential because both materials are considered biocompatible. Dozens or even hundreds of works have already been prepared on the subject of chitosan biocompatibility [1,2,36]. The amount of works on the FAU zeolite is not that extensive, but they clearly indicate the biocompatibility of this type of zeolite. Lutzweiler et al. proved that magnesium and calcium zeolites do not have cytotoxic properties [37]. A cytotoxicity study has already been carried out for the zeolite presented in this paper. The absence of zeolite toxicity was proven using MCF-7 cells. These results were presented in the work prepared by Jakubowski et al. [38]. Due to the fact that both the filler and the polymer are non-toxic, the foams prepared from them will also be non-toxic. As a comparative material for scaffold with calcium zeolite in the research, the scaffold containing hydroxyapatite, which is described in many scientific publications, was used. Photos of the scaffolds are shown in Figure 6. Their appearance is typical of this type of scaffold, and similar to others reported in many scientific publications [7,39]. At the bottom of Figure 6, there are photos showing chitosan disks, which were used in further stages of the research.

Figure 6. Scaffolds immediately after preparation (top) and scaffolds after cutting the disks (9 mm in diameter and 2.5 mm in height) used in the remaining studies (bottom). Ch-HA – scaffold with hydroxyapatite; Ch-CaX – scaffold with calcium zeolite X.

The first technique used to characterize scaffolds is FTIR (Figure 7). Most of the bands present are related to the structure of the chitosan. In the chitosan spectrum, a broad absorption band can be observed between 3500 and 3000 cm^{-1} , corresponding to -OH and -NH stretching frequencies [40]. The bands at ~ 2921 and $\sim 2860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to C-H symmetric and asymmetric stretching, respectively. These bands are typical characteristics of polysaccharides [41]. The presence of amide is confirmed by the band at around 1645 cm^{-1} . A band at $\sim 1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the N-H bending of the primary amine [42]. The CH_2 and CH_3 groups are confirmed by the presence of bands at ~ 1420 and $\sim 1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The band at 1150 cm^{-1} can be attributed

to asymmetric stretching of the C-O-C. The bands at 1065 and 1000 cm^{-1} correspond to C-O stretching.

Changes in spectra are visible both after adding hydroxyapatite and zeolite. The presence of hydroxyapatite is indicated by the additional band at $\sim 1025 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is connected with the vibrations of phosphate groups [43,44]. The presence of zeolite is indicated by bands in two ranges: 1042 – 840 cm^{-1} and 800 – 680 cm^{-1} . The first of them can be attributed to the asymmetric internal T-O stretching vibrations of the TO_4 tetrahedra of zeolite, where T is Si or Al [45]. While the bands in the second range are connected with the symmetric stretching vibration of Al-O in the Si-O-Al framework [46].

Figure 7. FTIR spectra of chitosan, chitosan-hydroxyapatite scaffold and chitosan-zeolite scaffold.

For the prepared scaffolds, photos were taken using an optical microscope, which is presented in Figure 8. As can be seen, both scaffolds are very porous materials. Based on these photos, there are no noticeable differences between the two materials.

Figure 8. The optical microscope images of the obtained scaffolds.

In the next step, the distribution of fillers in the chitosan matrix was determined using the SEM technique (Figure 9). Both types of scaffolds have a porous structure. In the case of scaffolds with the addition of hydroxyapatite, agglomeration of the filler is noticeable. Outside the place of large agglomeration, the filler is quite evenly distributed. On the basis of the analysis of the photos obtained for the scaffold with zeolite, it can be concluded that no filler agglomerates are formed. Zeolite is very evenly distributed throughout the entire volume of the scaffold. When analyzing the images at the highest magnification, single zeolite particles are visible. This even

distribution can result in comparable drug sorption in each volume and then even release.

Figure 9. SEM pictures of the chitosan-hydroxyapatite scaffold and chitosan-zeolite scaffold.

The Ch-CaX scaffold (375 %) has a higher swelling ratio than the Ch-HA scaffold (251 %). The differences in the swelling ratio for both scaffolds are not statistically significant (Figure 10). The swelling coefficient in the presented work can be considered typical. In literature reports, these values range from 150-650 % due to different methods of preparing scaffolds [47–49]. When the degree of degradation of both materials is compared, it can be seen that the differences between them are not statistically significant. The degradation of chitosan scaffolds is a common phenomenon, but there is a lot of research in the literature on the stabilization of these scaffolds by modifying them with various compounds that may also be applied in the future for the scaffolds proposed in this article [50].

Figure 10. Swelling ratio and degradation rate of Ch-HA and Ch-CaX.

The next stage of the research was to determine the ability of the obtained materials to sorption drugs for osteoporosis (Figure 11). The same studies were carried out for a chitosan scaffold without fillers, and the drug did not adsorb on it. As can be seen, the chitosan scaffold with zeolite retained almost twice as much drug as the chitosan scaffold with hydroxyapatite (these results are statistically significant.). This may be surprising because there is so much more calcium in hydroxyapatite, so there are also more places where the drug can attach. These results can be due to several aspects. The first is that hydroxyapatite agglomerates more, and hence the "availability" of calcium is less. The zeolite particles are evenly distributed, making them more accessible to the drug. Additionally, zeolite is a porous material, so even when it is partially covered by chitosan, the drug may permeate inside it.

Figure 11. Drug sorption on the chitosan-hydroxyapatite scaffold and chitosan-zeolite scaffold.

The most important information when preparing scaffolds with the function of releasing drugs is how the drug is released. The results of the release of risedronate from both materials are shown in Figure 12. The release results for both materials are significantly different. At first glance, the hydroxyapatite scaffold may appear to be better because it released more drug within 30 days. However, while considering the doses released, it can be seen that almost half of the drug is released on the first day. Such a large amount of the drug can cause inflammation, and, instead of supporting osseointegration, it can prolong the patient's recovery. The situation is different for the zeolite-chitosan scaffold. As expected, the drug is released in small doses. There is no "burst release" phenomenon, which proves the great potential of this material. Additionally, within a month, the drug was not completely released and small doses will be released over the following days. In the literature, to the knowledge of the authors, there are no reports on the delivery of this drug at such comparable small doses. To some extent, similar studies were presented by Mostafa et al. [51]. In their work, they used scaffolds prepared from chitosan/polyvinyl alcohol loaded with/without risedronate and nano-bioactive glass. They demonstrated drug release and the positive effect of drug scaffold on osseointegration. The advantage of the scaffold with calcium zeolite presented in this work is that in the initial hours the drug is also released in small doses.

Figure 12. Release of risedronate from the chitosan-hydroxyapatite scaffold and chitosan-zeolite scaffold.

Conclusions

In the presented work, a biocompatible chitosan-zeolite scaffold was prepared, and then the sorption of the drug for osteoporosis was performed on it. It was shown that the zeolite is evenly distributed throughout the entire volume of the scaffold, which will have a significant impact on the uniform sorption and release of the drug from materials potentially applicable in bone tissue engineering. The zeolite scaffolds retained almost twice as much drug as those with hydroxyapatite. This is because hydroxyapatite is more agglomerated and, in addition, zeolites have pores in which the drug can permeate. The most important aspect of this work was the evaluation of the possibility of releasing the drug for osteoporosis from the obtained materials. Admittedly, more of the drug was released from the scaffold with hydroxyapatite within 30 days, but the

dose released on the first day is about half of the total amount retained, due to which "burst release" is shown here, which is not the desired phenomenon for these drugs. From the scaffold with the addition of zeolite, the drug is slowly released in small doses, which is desirable and confirms the theoretical assumptions of this work. Risedronate is a widely investigated drug with excellent properties in the treatment of osteoporosis, the disadvantage of which is toxicity in excessively high doses, but a solution to this problem has been proposed in this paper. The scaffold obtained, because of its properties, has a very high potential for the controlled release of drugs for osteoporosis and bone tissue engineering. Due to the poor mechanical properties of chitosan scaffolds, the next step will be to place the material described in this paper into the pores of 3D-printed titanium and create a hybrid implant. The material described in this work will be responsible in such a hybrid implant for drug release and increasing osseointegration, while titanium alloy will be responsible for mechanical properties.

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Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

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